

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF INFORMATION TRANSMISSION IN INTERNET JOURNALISM

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Abstract. *In this article, I will show that Internet journalism combines the possibilities of press, radio, and television as the fastest media, and now you don't have to wait for a newspaper to be published or a news program to start on TV or radio to get information. I will tell you that the largest Internet publications are using elements such as text, photos, images, sound, and infographics to convey messages interactively.*

Key words: *modern forms of internet journalism, false information, several flaws and problems in internet journalism.*

СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПЕРЕДАЧИ ИНФОРМАЦИИ В ИНТЕРНЕТ-ЖУРНАЛИСТИКЕ

Аннотация. *В этой статье я покажу, что интернет-журналистика объединяет возможности прессы, радио и телевидения как самых быстрых СМИ, и теперь вам не нужно ждать выхода газеты или начала новостной программы на ТВ или радио, чтобы получить информацию. Я расскажу вам, что крупнейшие интернет-издания используют такие элементы, как текст, фотографии, изображения, звук и инфографику для интерактивной передачи сообщений.*

Ключевые слова: *современные формы интернет-журналистики, ложная информация, ряд недостатков и проблем в интернет-журналистике.*

INTRODUCTION

Journalism is a wide-ranging, thought-provoking field that is always in the center of innovation. Its role is incomparable in ensuring the establishment of democratic values in society, prompt and truthful information about events, rule of law, diversity of views, freedom of speech and opinion.

Internet journalism has undergone an unprecedented revolution in the past two decades. Therefore, it has become an urgent issue to quickly look carefully at this period, to ask many new questions, to study not only the future of the profession, but also its place and position now.

In the first period when internet journalism appeared in Uzbekistan, its prospects seemed abstract. Internet journalism in Uzbekistan began to take shape in the mid-2000s. It was definitely a process related to technical progress. At that time, in the Uzbek segment of Internet journalism, news sites were numbered on the fingers. More than half of them were opposition sites. [1]

The first national internet festival was held in Uzbekistan in 2005. The site uzreport.com, which is the basis of the current Uzreport TV, took the 2nd place in the direction of news publications. The sites ranked first and third are currently down.

The rapid development of information technologies has led to the development and popularization of Internet journalism in our country. Currently, Internet journalism has taken the

first place in the mass media of Uzbekistan in terms of its speed, the number of its audience and the width of its sphere of influence.[2]

Today, the role of Internet journalism in keeping up with modern information, studying, transmitting and improving it is extremely incomparable.

What kind of innovations and advantages does internet journalism have over regular journalism?

- Interactivity. Such a feature is inherent in the Internet technology itself, in which it provides its own versatile "networking".

- Professional approach. In doing so, it allows each student or group to take into account their own personal views, opinions and requirements.

- Orientation to the press. In this case, every student has the opportunity to get the information he wants, to the extent he wants, and to learn and analyze it to the extent he wants.

- Instantaneous. The advantage of this is that, in addition to the extremely high speed of data transfer, the necessary information reaches the place of transmission quickly and at the same time with high quality.

- Dimensionality. This allows readers to quickly and easily determine the importance of this or that information.

- Agreeableness. This means the ability to quickly and conveniently update the information page, taking into account the opinion of each visitor.

- Economy. Despite the high cost of Internet information dissemination, the necessary information reaches each reader faster and cheaper than paper information, and most importantly, in good quality.[3]

Including, it is appropriate to dwell on the professional advantages of journalists. First of all, the editorial organization of the media product has become a partial disadvantage. It was the editorial structure that created the "inertial adaptation" effect, as a result of which, despite the changes in consumer behavior, the media continued to insist on the old forms of communication, the traditional method of discrete production, and neglected interactivity.

After the introduction of the rotary printing press in 1844, the most significant changes in the journalism profession occurred in the 20th century.[4]

Apart from them, it is appropriate to talk about the unofficial messages that are spreading on the Internet today. In the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is no separate legal document that combats false news spread on the Internet. However, there are a number of legal documents that regulate the spheres of information, information and advertising, and the activities of mass media. Therefore, based on the experience of the studied foreign countries, it is possible to eliminate the legal gaps that have arisen by making changes and additions to the existing legislation.

In practice, there is a situation against spreading false information in our country:

persons who pretend to be poor, seriously ill, or treat such patients, who aim to get rich at the expense of good people's donations, can be qualified with the crime of fraud defined in Article 168 of the Criminal Code, based on the fact that they aim to gain wealth by abusing people's trust;

In order to create a feeling of panic and fear among people, false information about the commission of a terrorist act can be qualified as a crime of false reporting defined in Article 237 of the Criminal Code.

However, there are gaps in the legislation in a number of cases:

disseminating false information about disasters (natural or other) in order to create a feeling of panic, fear and protest against the state among the population;

disseminating false and unverified information about the tragedies that actually happened in order to cause panic among the population;

Issues of responsibility for informing false factors about the perpetrators of the incident, for example, showing persons who are not actually involved in the incident as participants in the incident, as the perpetrators of the incident, are not specified in the legislation.[5]

A good 21st century journalist tells factual stories about the real world around them using text, audio, visuals, and their stories are designed to be easy for people to relate to, share, and easily share. use them in other ways. In order to understand the kind of society we live in, it is very important to answer the question about the place of journalism and journalist as a professional in our life and attitude, in our worldview, in the space of personal life. This process is not simple and ambiguous, because the modern man in society gradually loses his exclusivity, his uniqueness, he becomes a part of mass consumer society, and in politics he is less and less taken into account by decision-makers.[6]

CONCLUSION

Of course, journalism must rely on the truth. Choosing a fact for a journalistic material is the first step of a journalist to express his opinion about that fact. But on the other hand, today's audience, which can pick up the same fact from non-journalistic sources, is no longer interested in a journalist who retells the truth. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the Russian tradition, which implies not only the impersonal communication of the fact, but also conveying a certain attitude towards it, giving a certain assessment to this fact. Therefore, in the sea of facts, there must be some mechanisms that allow the journalist to find the right fact on which to base his journalistic material. What criteria and instructions should a journalist have in the process of searching for this fact? In my opinion, this is professionalism and etiquette. In journalism, these two things cannot be separated, because a journalist does not work for one person, but for a very large audience. Journalism seems to be a rather complex profession, given that a journalist must not only report facts and opinions about them, but also understand the possible social impact of these reports. I think that today it is relevant to talk about journalism and social work precisely because journalists, first of all, work to inform society and achieve social impact.

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